

GUTTA

Saving fuel emissions
from maritime
Transport in the
Adriatic region

*Towards a sustainable
transportation in the Adriatic Sea*

Republika Hrvatska
**MINISTARSTVO MORA,
PROMETA I INFRASTRUKTURE**

Autorità di Sistema Portuale
del Mare Adriatico Meridionale
Bari, Brindisi, Manfredonia, Barletta, Monopoli

The project

GUTTA aims to reduce CO2 emissions from maritime transport in the Adriatic Sea.

The project will focus on ferry lines and will have three specific objectives:

- 1) Reducing CO2 emissions by a smart application based on meteorological forecasts
- 2) Supporting the process of Monitoring-Reporting-Verifying of CO2 emissions
- 3) Preparing the ground for a new cross-border route between Italy and Croatia

GUTTA will also establish a communication channel with citizens and professionals, resulting in a visible change in cross-border connectivity and territorial cohesion.

Project duration
01/01/2019-30/06/2021

Total Budget
1.200.000,00 EUR

European Union's contribution
1.020.000,00 EUR

GUTTA Specific Objectives

- ① To realize a pilot-system for planning ferry routes that minimize the CO2 emissions
- ② To support the EU-MRV regulation 757/2015 on maritime CO2 emissions
- ③ To facilitate the establishment of a new Italy-Croatia cross-border route

<https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/gutta>

Paper by: IGEPA group

